

OPTICAL PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENTS OF NCF: INFLUENCE OF MATERIAL PROPERTIES ON THE 2D PREFORM PERMEABILITY

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Abstract

To optimize the resin transfer molding (RTM)-tool loading process textile preforms are used. Textile preforming includes cutting, stitching and assembling the single textile layers to a preform. The preforming process reduces the manual work and in this regards the liquid composite molding process (LCM)-cycle time. In this paper the influence of yarn count and the stitching pattern on the 2D non crimp fabrics (NCF) preform permeability are investigated. A full automated optical permeameter was used to conduct 2D permeability measurements for glass and carbon fiber based preforms. This paper presents the reveal influence of the stitching pattern and the yarn count on the NCF preform permeability. The measurement series showed very low standard deviations. Additionally a comparison between the experimental filling time (measurement) and the predicted filling time (simulation) is presented.

1 Introduction

Carbon fibered reinforced plastic (CFRP) parts are used in the aerospace and automotive sector to reduce the application weight. CFRP parts are not only used for weight reduction, they also have very good mechanical properties, if the fibers are load specific orientated. In the past most of the composite components in the aeronautical industry are manufactured with preimpregnated fibers (preg) and the very expensive autoclave technology [1]. Nowadays CFRP parts are also manufactured with the liquid composite molding process (LCM). The LCM technique such as resin transfer molding (RTM) is a widely used technology to produce fiber based polymer composites [2; 3]. Modern composite production processes like the RTM technology

receives a lot of interest from industry and applied research. The industry asks for high quality components with good surface finish, good mechanical properties, excellent dimensional tolerances and low tooling costs [4; 5]. The RTM process starts with assembling dry fiber reinforcements to a preform (stack of dry fiber textiles). In the next step the preform is placed in a mold and the liquid medium, the matrix, a mixture of resin and hardener, is injected by constant pressure or flow rate. After the curing phase the CFRP part can be demolded and can be post processed [1; 2].

In order to obtain the best product quality, a completely filled mold is mandatory. The industry wants to assure the cost-effectiveness of the RTM process and the shortest possible mold filling time. To ensure the minimum process cycle time, the position of the resin injection points and air vents must be known.

In the past most time the mold design was optimized by trial-and-error. Nowadays flow simulation tools are replacing the very expensive trial-and-error procedure. The numerical filling simulation, which helps the engineer to optimize the tool design and to predict the mold filling time, is a very important supporting technical tool for the further development of the RTM process [1; 6]. For a perfect simulation set up it is necessary to have correct input parameters of the resin viscosity, the preform porosity and the preform permeability. The most important factor for a filling study is the knowledge about the permeability behavior of the textile preform because it is directly related to the impregnation and filling time [6–8]. For permeability measurements there are no standardized measurement systems available on the

market and according measurement methods are not industrialized. There are three different methods to obtain the permeability behavior of a dry fiber based preform, the linear, the radial and the trough thickness injection method. During the linear method the matrix is injected by a linear gate into a rectangular preform, so the flow front moves forward parallel to the injection line (one dimensional flow). If the resin is injected in the middle of a preform via a point, the radial injection method is used (two dimensional flow). Because of the anisotropic flow behavior of the preform the flow front moves radial and an ellipse occurs on the preform surface, given in Fig. 1 [1; 9].

Fig. 1: Online approximated ellipse during a permeability measurement of a CF preform

For continuous measurement of the 2D flow behavior of a textile preform a dielectric capacity or an optical permeameter can be used. Afterwards for the permeability calculation it is necessary to have the major and minor axes length of the spreading ellipse as a function of time. The literature depicts a lot of permeability studies with a dielectric capacity permeameter [8; 10–12].

In this study the flow behavior of carbon and glass fiber preforms is determined. The measurements are elaborated using a *full automated optical 2D permeameter*. The flow front is tracked by a monochromatic camera system.

2 Theoretical background

2.1 Permeability and Darcy's law

If a fiber preform gets saturated with a liquid medium, the fluid follows the path of least resistance. The resistance of a fiber preform to the fluids flow is called permeability. The most ground breaking equation for permeability calculation and the flow behaviour through porous media is Darcy's

law [4; 6; 13]. It is the generally accepted equation (Eq.1) to describe the one dimensional flow through a porous medium,

$$v_0 = - \frac{K \Delta P}{\eta \Delta x} \quad (1)$$

where v_0 is the superficial velocity (m/s), K is the permeability (m^2), η is the fluid viscosity (Pa s), ΔP is the imposed pressure difference (Pa) and Δx is the flow length in (m). A formulation for the two dimensional flow is described by Adams and Rebenfeld as well as by Hoes et al. [4; 14].

2.2 Influences on the Permeability

The fluid viscosity [13] and injection pressure [2; 10] of the fluid have no significant influence on the permeability behaviour of the unsaturated flow.

The most significant influence on the permeability is given by the fibre volume fraction, the porosity and the compaction behaviour [15; 16]. In the past, authors showed that the stitching pattern and the stitching direction take a significant influence on the permeability behavior of woven fabrics as well [11; 12]. The yarn count (also called the titer), number of filaments of a roving, has an influence on the permeability and on the anisotropy coefficient of a woven fabric too [10].

3 Experimental

3.1 Materials and testing plan

The fiber textiles used for this study are four different glass and four different carbon fiber based NCF reinforcements built up anisotropically. The NCF were manufactured by SAERTEX. The preforms fit accurately to 400 mm by 300 mm geometry of the cavity dimension. To eliminate the through thickness saturation (three dimensional flow) a hole of 13 millimetres was punched in the middle of the preform.

With both fiber types the influences of yarn count and stitching pattern on the NCF preform permeability was investigated. The permeability of the major and minor axes was determined at different fiber volume fractions. The fiber volume fraction was calculated by following equation (Eq.2) [8; 10; 17]:

$$V_f = \frac{n * \xi}{1000 * d * \rho_f} \quad (2)$$

where V_f is the fiber volume fraction (%), n is the number of layers (1), ξ is the fabric area weight (g/m^2), ρ_f fibre density (g/cm^3) and d is the cavity height (mm).

3.1.1 Influence of yarn count on the NCF preform permeability

The first glass fiber textile used for the permeability characterization was a triaxial fabric with a linear yarn density of 2400 tex in the 0° layer and a linear density of 300 tex in the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers. To see an influence of the yarn count on the NCF preform permeability a second triaxial fabric with a linear density in the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers of 600 tex was used. Both textile fabrics had an aerial weight of $1175 \text{ g}/\text{m}^2$.

Two biaxial carbon fibered based textile fabrics with an area weight of $540 \text{ g}/\text{m}^2$ and an orientation of $\pm 45^\circ$ layers were used to get the information about the influence of the yarn count on the NCF preform permeability. The first textile had a linear density of 12000 tex and the second textile had 24000 tex in both layers.

3.1.2 Influence of stitching pattern on the NCF preform permeability

To get the evidence of the influence of the stitching pattern on the biaxial glass fiber preform permeability two textiles with an area weight of $960 \text{ g}/\text{m}^2$ but with different stitching pattern were used. The first UD fabric was stitched together with tricot pattern and the second UD fabric was stitched together with a combination of a tricot-franse pattern.

The carbon fibered NCF reinforcements had an area weight of $410 \text{ g}/\text{m}^2$. The difference between these both textiles is the stitching pattern. The first textile had a tricot, and the second a franse pattern. Fig. 2 shows a glass fiber preform, which is stitched together with a tricot pattern. This pattern is mainly used for UD or for biaxial $0^\circ/90^\circ$ NCF preforms, because the stitching yarn can cross the whole fiber bundle and fix them together.

Fig. 3 depicts a carbon fiber based biaxial NCF preform stitched together with a franse pattern. A franse pattern is generally used to fix $\pm 45^\circ$ layers together.

Fig. 2: Tricot stitching pattern of a biaxial NCF glass fiber preform

Fig. 3: Franse stitching pattern of a biaxial NCF carbon fiber preform

3.1.2 Liquid medium: Plant oil

As liquid medium coloured plant oil was used because it has a similar viscosity as resin during processing has. To measure the permeability of carbon fiber fabrics it is needed to dye the plant oil with a non-polar colour. The used colour was SUDANRED IV (Sigma Aldrich GmbH). For the viscosity determination a couette rheometer was used. The viscosity was determined in a temperature range between 15°C and 30°C to have the valid viscosity value for the permeability calculation.

3.2 Permeability measurement set up

For the 2 dimensional permeability characterization an optical permeameter was used. The optical permeameter is shown in Fig. 4. It consists of a mold with the cavity dimensions of 400 mm by 300 mm, a composite glass plate as upper mold tool with 40 mm thickness, a lower steel plate with an injection hole in the middle, a pressure pot with the fluid and

a camera system with a monochromatic camera. A 35 mm thick steel frame is used to compensate the mold deflection due to the high injection and compaction pressure.

Fig. 4: Optical permeameter

To identify systematically the ideal geometry and thickness of the reinforcing steel frame and maximum glass thickness the finite element method (FEM) was used. The boundary conditions for the steel frame are given by the injection and compaction pressure. It is allowed to measure with an injection pressure of six bars and a fiber volume content of up to 63 % which corresponds to a compaction pressure of five bars [17]. The optimum assembly of the glass plate and the reinforcing steel frame is shown in Fig. 5. The configuration of a 40 mm composite glass plate and a 35 mm thick steel frame ensures a constant cavity height during the permeability measurement. After the mold is closed the reinforcing steel frame is placed on the top of the glass plates and it is screwed to the bottom edges of the lower mold tool. For the permeability measurements different cavity heights are available to characterize the permeability behaviour at several fiber volume fractions. The camera is arranged on the top of the optical permeameter and continuously pictures of the spreading flow front are captured. The pressure source ensures constant injection pressure in the pressure pot. During the infiltration the main axes of the developing ellipse are

determined online and are stored for the successive permeability evaluation.

Fig. 5: FEM analysis for the reinforcing steel frame and the determined glass plate thickness

After the infiltration a LabVIEW® program determines the major and minor radius of the elliptic flow front. This information is used to calculate the permeability of the major and minor axes.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Influence of yarn count on the NCF preform permeability

4.1.1 GF-preforms

Fig. 6 shows the influence of the yarn count on the triaxial NCF glass fiber preform permeability. K1 represents the permeability of the major axis and K2 is the permeability of the minor axis.

Fig. 6: Influence of yarn count on the triaxial NCF glass fiber preform permeability

Two triaxial glass fiber based preforms with different yarn counts in the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers but with the same yarn count in the 0° layer, same area weight, the same fiber volume fraction and the same fiber type are compared. The corresponding comparison shows, that K1 and K2 increase with decreasing yarn count. The permeability of the major axis is four times higher for 300 tex compared to 600 tex. Also K2 increases as yarn count decreases. The influence on the permeability of the minor axis is less pronounced compared to the major axis permeability; K2 approximately doubles when the yarn count is decreased from 600 tex per $\pm 45^\circ$ layer to 300 tex per $\pm 45^\circ$ layer.

4.1.2 CF-preforms

The effect of yarn count on permeability (K1 and K2) of biaxial carbon fiber NCF preforms is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: Influence of yarn count on the biaxial NCF carbon fiber preform permeability

The yarn count changes in $\pm 45^\circ$ layer from 12000 tex to 24000 tex. As elaborated for the triaxial glass fiber based NCF preforms the effects on permeability are the same for biaxial carbon fiber NCF preforms. The decreasing yarn count is responsible for the increasing permeability in the major and minor axis. K1 rises by a factor of 1.3 and K2 increases by a factor of 1.5 using a textile with less yarn count.

The permeability characterization of glass and carbon fiber preforms showed, that in both cases the permeability of the major and minor axis are increasing, if the yarn count is decreasing.

4.2 Influence of the stitching pattern on the NCF preform permeability

4.2.1 GF-preforms

Fig. 8 shows that also the stitching pattern has a significant influence on the NCF glass fiber preform permeability's. The stitching pattern has a very large influence on the minor axis permeability. The K2 value from a preform with a tricot pattern is one and a half time higher as the K2 value of a preform with a combination of tricot and franse pattern. K1 similarly increases by a factor of 3.5 from a tricot/franse pattern to a tricot pattern.

Fig. 8 Influence of stitching pattern on the biaxial NCF glass fiber preform permeability

4.2.2 CF-preforms

Fig. 9 presents the influence of the stitching pattern on the NCF carbon fiber preform permeability.

Fig. 9: Influence of stitching pattern on the biaxial NCF carbon fiber preform permeability

The preforms with the tricot pattern have a one and a half times higher permeability of major axis as the preforms of the minor axis. The minor axis preform permeability increases also with the tricot pattern by a factor of 1.3.

This measurement series showed the influence of the stitching pattern on the NCF preform permeability. The preform permeability, K1 and K2, increases if the preform is stitched together with a tricot pattern, because the tricot pattern creates bigger gaps between the single rovings, seen in figure 2.

4.3 Measurement vs. simulation

After the permeability calculation, which is based on Darcy’s law, a simulation software, PAM-RTM®, was used to monitor the permeability estimations of K1 and K2. A random single glass fiber preform permeability measurement of the testing plan, given in Fig. 10, was selected for the flow simulation. The geometry of the measured preform was 300 mm by 400 mm, the cavity height was 3.5 mm and the fiber volume fraction was 55%.

Fig. 10: Permeability characterization of a glass fiber NCF preform

It can be seen that the measurement stopped 15 mm on the left and on the right side before the oil reached the end of the preform. To this point in time the whole impregnation process lasted 473 sec. It was the last captured image of the sequence.

Every simulation starts with the creation of a model. Therefore, in the first phase of the simulation, a meshed plate was designed. The dimension of the 2D model is the ones of the preform, meshed with 2 mm triangle elements. The simulation set up is based to the data given in table 1.

To get the time, when the flow front is 15 mm away from the left edge, a pressure sensor is responsible to detect the flow front. In Fig. 11 the pressure sensor which is added in the model and the injection hole can be seen.

Table 1: Input parameters for the flow simulation

K1 [m ²]	K2 [m ²]	Viscosity [mPa]	Porosity [1]	Injection pressure [bar]
2.4E-11	8.9E-12	65	0.45	1

Fig. 11: 2D meshed plate with pressure sensor and injection hole

After setting the boundary conditions for the injection pressure the simulation started.

The result of the filling simulation, shown in Fig. 12, represents the expected filling time. The flow front reaches the pressure point after 482 sec.

Fig. 12: Result of the filling simulation

The simulation has demonstrated that the permeability calculation is in quite good correlation with the experimental result. It can be seen that both ellipses have the same shape. Due to mesh errors or too coarse mesh sizes the flow simulation results slightly higher filling time than the real process.

Fig. 13 presents a filling simulation of a vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) process. The mapped part is an under body structure of a car. The lay up is according to the customer's specific requirements. The under body structure is a sandwich lay up and the result of this simulation was the perfect determination for the injection and vent positions.

Fig. 13: Filling simulation of an under body structure

5 Conclusions

The main focus of this study has been to characterize the in plane permeability's of glass and carbon fiber based NCF preforms with an optical permeameter. For meaningful results, the permeability's were determined at different fiber volume fractions with low standard deviations. With the used optical permeameter it is allowed to measure preforms with an injection pressure of six bars and a fiber content of up to 63%. For all the measurements the colored test fluid (plant oil) was injected with a constant injection pressure of one bar.

All permeability measurements have a very less standard deviation. The standard deviation is all over smaller than 10% or even smaller for the permeability's of major and minor axes. The lowest deviation is established by the carbon fiber based biaxial NCF preforms. Therefore the standard deviation is lower than 6% for K1 and lower than 3% for K2 values. Only one textile shows a higher standard deviation. The permeability measurements of the triaxial glass fiber NCF preforms have a standard deviation of more than 17% for K1 and K2.

In the first measurement series the influence of yarn count on the NCF preform permeability was determined. The permeability characterizations were performed with both fiber types. The influence of yarn count is confirmed. With an increasing yarn

count the permeability of the major and minor axis are decreasing. That means, that the mould filling time increases as well by the same fiber volume fraction.

The second part of this study was to determine the influence of the stitching pattern on the NCF preform permeability. After this study it can also be said, that the matrix flow in LCM processes is highly affected by the used stitching pattern. Using the tricot pattern the permeability's, K1 and K2 are mainly affected.

An implementation of a filling simulation with PAM-RTM® was the last part of this study. A comparison of a real filling process (glass NCF, tricot pattern, fiber volume fraction 55%) with the simulation has shown that both filling times are nearly the same.

In conclusion, individual preforms, which are different in yarn counts or stitching pattern, will typically influence the mould filling times.

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